

Modern Methods of Treatment of Sinusitis

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Abstract: Septoplasty is a surgical procedure that corrects a deformed nasal septum. Despite the fact that septoplasty is a surgical operation, it is the least traumatic procedure. The procedure not only eliminates external defects, but also preserves the bone and cartilage tissue without any damage.

Key words: Nasal dryness, Hearing impairment, Allergy.

When is septoplasty necessary?

The most important symptom of a deviated nasal septum is difficult nasal breathing, regardless of chronic nasal congestion. It is very important for a person to breathe through the nose, because after passing through the nasal passages, the air is cleaned of impurities before entering the lungs directly. Nasal breathing is a direct prevention of many different diseases: bronchitis, asthma, heart and other important organs in the body.

Deviation of the septum makes natural breathing very difficult or completely impossible. Adolescent and young patients may not experience significant breathing difficulties. This greatly complicates the diagnosis, but does not exclude possible consequences due to the deformation of the septum.

Often, those suffering from a deviation of the nasal septum suffer from persistent inflammation of the respiratory tract and sinuses, sinusitis and other diseases. Often, along with diseases of the nasal passages, throat diseases are observed: pharyngitis, tonsillitis, laryngitis, etc., which can later become chronic.

Sometimes people start self-medicating by buying drops for a runny nose or sore throat medicine at the pharmacy, which leads to temporary, but not permanent, recovery.

If the deformation of the septum occurs due to an injury to the nose, a significant change in its shape may occur. In such cases, a person often has bleeding and other problems related to septal disorders. Other symptoms of curvature may include:

Dryness in the nose.

Impaired hearing.

Allergy.

Deterioration of hearing is due to the fact that the complex breathing through the nose stops keeping enough oxygen in the middle ear. If a person experiences one or more of these symptoms, an ENT specialist comes to the rescue and diagnoses, prescribes treatment, or orders surgery. If the deformation of the nasal septum is small, laser or radio wave methods of septoplasty can be used.

Deformation factors

The septum is represented by osteochondral tissue, dividing the nasal cavity into equal halves. When this region is deformed, its position shifts from the central boundary line. This fact causes a lot of problems for a person and can even lead to health problems, that is, chronic diseases (rhinitis,

sinusitis, etc.). The deformation of the tissues described above also causes difficulty in breathing through the nose, snoring, intermittent breathing and shortness of breath. Sometimes bleeding occurs. If the septum deviates due to injury, the shape of the nose will change after healing.

There are many factors that lead to deformation of the nasal septum. Among them are both physiological and traumatic properties of the body:

Physiological.

This reason is recognized by doctors as one of the most common among patients who decide to undergo septoplasty. The physiological factor refers to the uneven growth of the tissues that make up the nasal septum during the general growth of the human body. Usually, such a septum is completely curved or shifted to one side, or there may be peculiar protrusions on it.

Compensatory.

For the deformation of the septum, these factors include: the presence of a foreign object in the nasal cavity (piercing), chronic rhinitis in the patient, the appearance of various neoplasms, for example, adenoids.

Traumatic.

This is a less well-known cause of the abnormal position of the nasal septum, which is usually found in professional athletes. In some cases, other professionals who are bruised or hit due to falls or accidents also suffer from injuries. Traumatic types of septal deformation include mechanical damage: cracks and other types of damage. Any injury, even small or during childhood, can lead to a violation of the growth and curvature of the nasal septum in the future.

However, regardless of what is behind the displacement of the nasal septum, it can be corrected today only with the help of surgery - septoplasty.

Types of operations

The procedure in question is performed using different methods: conventional surgical method and laser technology. The endoscopic type of operation is the most common due to its speed and safety, but we will consider both methods in order.

Laser correction.

This type of operation is characterized by the correction of a deformed septum using "laser radiation". The procedure is performed under local anesthesia and is bloodless and painless. Laser rays have antiseptic properties, as a result of which the risk of infectious infections in the postoperative period is reduced to almost zero. Recovery after laser surgery is quick without special tampons. After the operation, a person does not need to stay in a medical facility overnight. The time of the procedure does not exceed 30 minutes, the operation is performed in an outpatient setting. Despite all the advantages of the laser method, it has contraindications and is ineffective in some particularly difficult cases.

Endoscopic correction.

This type of septoplasty is a mild surgical intervention. The procedure is performed on the mucous membrane, which ensures that there are no surgical scars on the outside of the face. Modern possibilities of performing this type of operations allow not only to avoid intervention traces and preserve the beauty of the face, but also to significantly reduce the duration of the postoperative period. The endoscopic type of operation involves the resection of small areas of osteochondral tissue, which prevents its normal condition and function. However, in some cases (especially if the patient has a traumatic deformity factor), it is very important to destroy some elements of the cartilaginous tissue. Usually, endoscopic septoplasty takes up to 45 minutes, including the preparation of the person for the operation. Endoscopic surgery is used only in cases where it is necessary to remove individual tissue elements that prevent the formation of the natural position of the nasal septum.

The effectiveness and contraindications of the procedure

The correction is made through small incisions in the inner cavity of the nose. The appearance and shape of the section will be fixed. The final positive result of septoplasty is characterized by:

Quality of life improves. A beautiful, ideally shaped nose is guaranteed after surgery. Those who were previously embarrassed by their face can safely "turn their nose", because it will be really aesthetic.

Breathing through the nose is restored. If the operation was performed not for aesthetic reasons, but for medical reasons, the person can breathe calmly through the nose again.

Guaranteed relief from various ailments. Such diseases include chronic ENT diseases caused by septal deformation.

It should be noted that the operation called septoplasty is not performed to change the shape of the nose. However, it can be combined with another type of surgery - rhinoplasty.

As a surgical method, septoplasty has a number of contraindications. The most important of them is poor blood coagulation, which is the main prohibition for performing any surgical operations.

Also, surgery for cancer, cardiovascular disease, diabetes or infectious diseases is not performed. It is not possible to perform the operation in minors, because the formation of the osteochondral tissue of the septum is not complete. Other possible contraindications (pregnancy, etc.) are discussed separately with the doctor.

Principle of operation

Before appointing the operation, the specialist conducts laboratory tests and examinations. The list of required tests and important exams includes:

Examination by an ENT specialist

Blood biochemistry

Cardiogram.

Diagnosis of blood clots.

General blood and urine tests.

Fluorography (if it has already been done this year, you must provide a picture).

Blood analysis.

Septoplasty is performed in several stages: the patient is prepared, local (or general) anesthesia is applied, after which a special incision is made in the nasal mucosa. Previously, it was necessary to cut the skin of the nose, but today this method of operation is considered insignificant and is used in exceptional cases.

After cutting, the soft tissues are separated and the curved elements of the cartilaginous tissue are resected, which interferes with establishing the natural position of the nasal septum. After all defects are eliminated, the septum is straightened by moving individual elements of bone and cartilaginous tissue.

After classic septoplasty, tampons are inserted into the nasal passages and a hard bandage is applied to them. Tampons are removed a few days after the operation, taking into account the individual characteristics of its implementation.

Rehabilitation period

Recovery after surgery is usually very quick. During the first 24 or 48 hours, special tampons remain in the nasal passages, their purpose is to reduce the risk of bleeding and stabilize the natural position of the septum. Some clinics offer the patient silicone tampons, which not only keep the

shape of the nose well, but also ensure almost complete absence of bleeding and do not interfere with breathing after the operation.

After removing tampons from the nose, it is very important to strictly follow all the instructions of the doctor about eating hot food and alcohol, smoking, increasing physical activity, visiting saunas and swimming pools.

To prevent post-operative infections and ease the patient's condition, the doctor prescribes pain-relieving and fever-reducing drugs, and sometimes it is necessary to inject antibiotics. After removing the tampons from the nasal passages, the doctor prescribes nasal drops to moisten the mucous membrane. Usually, such drugs are not only drops, but also sprays, and in some cases ointments are prescribed.

During the recovery process after surgery, the mucous membrane of the nose completely heals, and natural breathing is observed 3-4 weeks after the operation.

The recovery period after laser septoplasty lasts 1-2 weeks. Also, laser surgery does not require tampons or antiseptics. The full functioning of the patient is observed 7-10 days after the operation, because by this time the person is freed from tampons and a strong bandage. There are no external manifestations of the operation, such as bruises and swelling on the face. If you take proper care of your face during the rehabilitation period and follow all the doctor's instructions, recovery will not take much time and will not cause unnecessary discomfort.

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